

Recent Cross Section Measurements in MicroBooNE

Maitreyee Moudgalya

PhD Student at the University of Manchester

On behalf of the MicroBooNE Collaboration

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The MicroBooNE Detector

- A short baseline neutrino detector at Fermilab, USA.
- Receives neutrinos from two beams: BNB & NuMI
- Collected data from 2015-2021: accumulated over 800k neutrino interactions
- Published 82 papers + over 60 public notes

MicroBooNE LArTPC Detector

MicroBooNE is an 85-tonne active volume Liquid Argon Time Projection Chamber.

Fully active tracking calorimeter:

- 3 wire planes that collect ionization charge
- 32 PMTs that collect scintillation light
- 3D neutrino interaction reconstruction

Precision neutrino measurements at scale:

- mm-level resolution, ns-scale timing
- MeV-scale detection thresholds

Excellent particle identification (PID):

- topological and calorimetric
- Electron and photon separation
- Muon, proton and pion separation

One Detector & Two Beams

Booster Neutrino Beam (BNB)

- on-axis, primary beam
- 8 GeV protons, 1.3×10^{21} POT
- $\langle E_{\nu\mu} \rangle \sim 800$ MeV

Neutrinos at the Main Injector (NuMI)

- off-axis: 8° (target), 120° (absorber)
- 120 GeV protons, 2.0×10^{21} POT
- $\langle E_{\nu\mu} \rangle \sim 500$ MeV, $\langle E_{\nu e} \rangle \sim 700$ MeV
- higher ν_e content, $\sim 2.5\%$

MicroBooNE's Science Goals

Investigate the MiniBooNE Low Energy Excess
and search for BSM physics

Neutrino Interactions:
Precision measurements on argon

Detector Physics:
Advancing LArTPC technology

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Neutrino Interaction Modeling Challenge

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[Rev. Mod. Phys. 84, 1307 \(2012\)](#)

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E_ν

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- Many known unknowns that must be accurately simulated:
 - Ground states, Fermi motion
 - Neutrino interaction mechanisms
 - Final state interactions (FSI)
 - ...

arXiv:2201.04664

[Rev. Mod. Phys. 84, 1307 \(2012\)](#)

E_ν

ν -Ar Cross Sections

Neutrino oscillation measurements and BSM searches are limited by the mismodeling of ν -Ar interactions.

- Crucial inputs for LArTPC experiments like SBN and DUNE.
- Broad xsec programme @ MicroBooNE – 31 publications to-date and many more ongoing analyses.

MicroBooNE Cross Section Publications

Inclusive Measurements

- ν_μ -Ar Multiplicity @ BNB: [EPJC 79 248 \(2019\)](#)
- 1D ν_μ CC Inclusive @ BNB: [PRL 123 131801 \(2019\)](#), [PRL 128 151801 \(2022\)](#)
- 2D ν_μ CC Inclusive @ BNB: [PRL 133 041801 \(2024\)](#), [PRD 110 L013006 \(2024\)](#)
- 3D ν_μ CC Inclusive @ BNB: [PLB 870 139939 \(2025\)](#)
- 1D ν_e CC Inclusive @ NuMI: [PRD 104 052002 \(2021\)](#), [PRD 105 051102 \(2022\)](#)

Pionless Measurements

- 1D, 2D ν_μ CC 0π Np @ BNB: [PRD 102 112013 \(2020\)](#), [PRD 112 072007 \(2025\)](#), [PRD 112 112004 \(2025\)](#)
- 1D ν_μ CC 0π 1p @ BNB: [PRL 125 201803 \(2020\)](#)
- 1D, 2D ν_μ CC 0π 1p TKI @ BNB: [PRL 131 101802 \(2023\)](#), [PRD 108 053002 \(2023\)](#)
- 1D, 2D ν_μ CC 0π 1p GKI @ BNB: [PRD 109 092007 \(2024\)](#)
- 1D, 2D ν_μ CC 0π 1p Neutrino Direction @ BNB: [PRD 111 113007 \(2025\)](#)
- 1D ν_μ CC 0π 2p @ BNB: [arXiv:2211.03734](#) (accepted PLB)
- 1D ν_e CC 0π Np @ BNB: [PRD 106 L051102 \(2022\)](#)
- 1D ν_e CC 0π Np @ NuMI: [arXiv:2511.17342](#)

Pion Production Measurements

- 1D ν_μ CC $1\pi^0$ @ BNB: [PRD 99 091102 \(2019\)](#), [PRD 110 092014 \(2024\)](#)
- 1D, 2D ν_μ NC $1\pi^0$ @ BNB: [PRD 107 012004 \(2023\)](#), [PRL 134 161802 \(2025\)](#)
- 1D ν_μ CC $1\pi^\pm$ @ BNB: [arXiv:2509.03628](#) (accepted PRD)
- 1D ν_e CC $1\pi^\pm$ @ NuMI: [PRL 135 061802 \(2025\)](#)

Rare Processes

- Λ Production @ NuMI: [PRL 130 231802 \(2023\)](#)
- η Production @ BNB: [PRL 132 151801 \(2024\)](#)
- K^+ Production @ BNB: [PRL 135 251804 \(2025\)](#)

Novel Techniques

- MicroBooNE Genie Tune: [PRD 105 072001 \(2022\)](#)
- Neutron Identification: [EPJC 84 1052 \(2024\)](#)
- Model Validation: [PRD 111 092010 \(2025\)](#)

ν -Ar Cross Sections

This talk will cover 6 new analyses

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- 1D ν_e CC 0π Np @ NuMI: [arXiv:2511.17342](#)

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Pionless Measurements

ν_μ CC 0π w/ protons

- Semi-inclusive signal \rightarrow allows for high statistics
 - Pionless signal \rightarrow topological proxy for QE-like events
- \rightarrow Facilitates comparison across nuclear targets with other Cherenkov experiments that have high thresholds for hadronic activity.

- Good data-generator agreement for 1D measurements.
- Only a subset of generators adequately describe the data in the 2D measurements.
 - \rightarrow GiBUU 2025 performed best.

• More results in [PRD 112 072007 \(2025\)](#)

$0.48 \text{ GeV}/c \leq p_\mu < 0.7 \text{ GeV}/c$

ν_μ CC 0π $1p$

- Uses the QE-like signal to study the reconstructed neutrino direction (θ_{vis}) resolution.

→ Relevant to DUNE sub-GeV atmospheric oscillation studies.

- Prediction made by re-weighting BNB events to DUNE Honda atmospheric neutrino flux.

- Differential cross sections are sensitive to nuclear effects impacting direction determination:

- Low θ_{vis} - high QE contribution
- High θ_{vis} - multinucleon effects (MEC, RES, DIS)

- Preference for G18T that has tuning applied to QE contribution.

- More results in [PRD 111 113007 \(2025\)](#)

ν_e CC 0π Np

- Dominant channel for ν_e at $O(1 \text{ GeV})$
- More exclusive final state than previous ν_e results. Important because:
 - ν_e is appearance channel for oscillations @ long baselines, e.g. DUNE
 - Crucial for sterile neutrino searches

- Used the NuMI beam due to the higher ν_e content.
- Differential cross sections show good data-generator agreement as a function of:
 - electron energy
 - visible energy
 - electron-proton opening angle

• [arXiv:2511.17342](https://arxiv.org/abs/2511.17342) – submitted to PRD.

Pion Production Measurements

- First measurement of this channel on argon.
→ One of the dominant interaction modes at the energies of the DUNE neutrino flux.
- Leveraging the higher ν_e content in the full NuMI dataset.
- Overall good modeling of the data within uncertainties.
- More results in [PRL 135 061802 \(2025\)](#)

- First high-statistics measurement on argon.
- First measurement of pion momentum.
- Overall good data-generator agreement within uncertainties.
- Signs of mismodelling at low Q^2 and for high pion momenta driven by final state interactions.
- One of the dominant interaction modes at the energies of the DUNE neutrino flux.
- More results in [arXiv:2509.03628](https://arxiv.org/abs/2509.03628)

Rare Process Measurement

ν_μ CC K^+

- First measurement of K^+ on argon.
- Crucial for constraining the background for proton decay $p \rightarrow \nu K^+$ searches in DUNE.

- 10 candidate events found using BDT (red triangles).
- [PRL 135 251804 \(2025\)](#)

TABLE I. The $\nu_\mu + \text{Ar} \rightarrow \mu^- + K^+ + X$ cross section extracted from different neutrino event generators compared with the cross section extracted from data.

Generator	Cross section (10^{-42} cm ² /nucleon)
GENIE v2.12.10	8.67
GENIE v3.00.06	8.42
GENIE v3.4.0 (AR23)	9.85
GiBUU 2025, patch 1	6.52
NEUT 5.4.0.1 [51]	9.71
NuWro 19.02.1	10.87
MicroBooNE data	$7.93 \pm 3.22(\text{stat}) \pm 2.83(\text{syst})$

Summary

- MicroBooNE is a LArTPC detector at Fermilab.
- Actively analysing 5 years worth of data with two neutrino beams.
- Several recent cross section results covering pionless, pion production and rare process channels with unprecedented detail.
→ Critical for the physics goals of the broader LArTPC programme regarding DUNE and SBN.
- Many more results in the works – stay tuned!

September 2025 Collaboration Meeting @
University of Oxford

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